

Effect of Calcium Carbide as a Ripening Agent on the Nutritional Composition and Ripening Time of Banana Pulp

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Abstract— This study was carried out to examine the effect of calcium carbide as a fruit ripening agent on sensory properties, nutritive properties, metal composition and some antioxidant enzymes of banana pulp. Bananas were separated into 4 groups made up four (4) banana fingers each of approximately the same size. Calcium carbide was administered at two different concentrations (4g/kg) for Group 2 and (8g/kg) for Group 3. Group 1 was the unripe banana while Group 4 was a naturally ripened banana (Control). The results obtained revealed that calcium carbide is a very good ripening agent with a ripening time of 3days (72 hours) and 2days (48 hours) for Group 2 and Group 3 respectively. The results also showed that calcium carbide at (4g/kg) and (8g/kg) did not affect the sensory properties as there was no significant ($p \geq 0.05$) variation. There was a significant ($p \leq 0.05$) difference in the proximate values. Moisture contents of the bananas ranged from 69.40 ± 1.54 GRP 1 to 77.78 ± 0.80 in GRP 4, while crude protein ranged from 1.27 ± 0.01 in GRP 2 to 2.25 ± 0.13 in GRP 4. Ash content ranged from 1.59 ± 0.09 to 2.78 ± 0.13 with GRP 1 having the significant ($p \leq 0.05$) highest value. Total carbohydrate content ranged from 15.23 ± 0.92 in GRP 4 to 24.39 ± 3.04 in GRP 2. The result on mineral composition showed that there was a significant ($p \leq 0.05$) decrease in Pb content during ripening. GRP 4 banana had the lowest Pb value at 0.02 ± 0.01 , while GRP 1 had the highest values at 0.07 ± 0.01 . The highest contents of Zn and Mg at 6.08 ± 0.08 and 9.12 ± 0.37 respectively were recorded in GRP 4. There were significant ($p \leq 0.05$) difference in the Mn, Ca and Cd contents (2.42 ± 0.12 , 2.24 ± 0.20 and 1.46 ± 0.05 respectively) in the banana treated with 8 g/kg CaC₂ (GRP 3) when compared with the rest of the groups. Cu content ranged from 0.38 ± 0.01 in GRP 4 to 1.64 ± 0.09 in GRP 1. From the result of antioxidant enzyme activities, calcium carbide affected all the antioxidant enzymes activities (Catalase, peroxidase and Ascorbate peroxidase) at 4g/kg and 8g/kg as their concentrations significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) decreased the amount of the enzymes, when compared with the naturally ripened banana. The peroxidase activity was significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) higher in GRP 4 at 3.42 ± 0.05 U/mL than the rest of the groups. The ascorbate peroxidase activity was also highest in GRP 4 at 33.79 ± 2.15 U/mL. The catalase activity ranged from 0.38 ± 0.24 U/mL in GRP 3 to 0.68 ± 0.15 U/mL GRP 4. These results showed that even though calcium carbide may have fruit ripening ability, it also causes reduction in the fruit nutrients and antioxidant enzyme activities.

Keywords- Calcium carbide, Ripening agent, Ripening time, Nutritional quality, Mineral composition, Antioxidant enzyme, Banana

I. INTRODUCTION

Banana (*Musa spp.*) is one of the major crops which are cultivated in all over the world. Banana is grown in more than 120 countries throughout the tropical and subtropical regions (Molina and Vanmayor, 1999). It is considered as popular staple food for more than 400 million people (Sanjeev and Eswaran, 2008). India is the largest producer of banana with 23.205 million of annual productions (Kulkarni et al., 2010). Approximately 100,000 Sri Lankans engage with banana cultivation. The fruits are wholesome and fairly well balanced source of nutrients containing various mineral salts, high amount of carbohydrates with a little oil and protein (Ahenkoral et al., 1997). It gives high content of vitamins A and C but less in vitamins B (Margard and Briav, 1979). It has significant health benefits. It reduces risk of high blood pressure, reduces risk of stroke, cholesterol-lowering effect, great support to kidney health and has potential as a remedy for heart born and important to healthy teeth and bones, giving better contribution to body's immune system, promoting brain health and heart health (Kumar et al., 2012).

Banana is a climateric fruit showing an increase in respiration resulting in colour, flavor, aroma and texture changes. It is usually eaten raw when ripe and is a major starchy food common

in Sub-Sahara Africa and Asia, providing more than 25 % of carbohydrate (Adeniji et al., 2007). The consumption of banana cuts across every age group, from little children to adults, and it supplies necessary calories and essential micronutrients. Once harvested it is highly perishable, with short shelf life leading to high post-harvest losses of about 20-50 % due to poor handling and quality deterioration (Ajayi and Mbah, 2007; Zewter et al., 2012). In order to reduce the high post-harvest losses, bananas are harvested when green but mature, and artificially ripened when needed with the use of ripening agents.

Ripening agents are substances which hasten the ripening process, and it comes in different forms. These include ethylene gas, ethephon, ethylene glycol, etherel and calcium carbide (Singal et al., 2012); african bush mango fruit (*irvingia gabonesis*) and leaves, Palm nut, Cassia leaves, yellow Pawpaw leaves, torch light battery, calcium carbide, potash and ash (Ajayi and Mbah, 2007). African mango fruits, calcium carbide and newbouldia leaves were also reported by Adewole and Duruji (2010). According to Singal et al. (2012), the commercial practice is to use these ripening agents to artificially ripen the fruits at the destination market before retailing.

The use of calcium carbide has been in use for century and in most countries it has been in band but still in use in Nigeria, and

out of ignorance the public consume it without knowing what they are consuming. This project work is designed to create awareness to the public, making them know that the use of calcium carbide is very hazardous to their health. The aim of this work is to ascertain the effect of calcium carbide as a ripening agent on the ripening time and nutritional quality of banana.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. STUDY AREA

This study was conducted in Biochemistry Laboratory unit, Federal University of Agriculture, Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria.

B. COLLECTION OF SAMPLES

Freshly harvested bunch of green but mature unripe banana was gotten from the local market in Makurdi, Nigeria on market day when fresh produce were brought to the market for sale. The ripening agents used for the study was gotten from the same market.

C. BANANA GROUPING

The banana bunch was cut and separated into 4 groups made up four (4) banana fingers of approximately the same size each (0.08kg).

Group 1: unripe banana serve as negative control (NGC)

Group 2: ripened banana with 4 g of calcium carbide

Group 3: ripened banana with 8 g of calcium carbide

Group 4: naturally ripened banana serve as positive control (PTC)

D. SAMPLE PREPARATION

Group 1 banana did not undergo ripening process. 4 g and 8 g of calcium carbide was wrapped separately in polythene before being dropped into a black polythene bag containing the bananas in group 2 and group 3 respectively while the last group (group 4) was placed in the polythene bag without any ripening agent and used as the positive control sample. All the bags containing group 2, 3 and 4 bananas were tied up and stored in the same room. All the samples were monitored daily for colour changes of the peel indicative of ripening. The stage of ripeness was judged primarily by colour using a 1-7 scale common in the industry.

E. RIPENING TIME

Ripening time and shelf life was determined using a method described by Adeyemi et al., (2018).

F. SENSORY EVALUATION

Sensory analysis was carried out using the seven point hedonic scale (where 1=dislike much and 7=like much) as described by Linda et al. (1991). The organoleptic properties evaluated were appearance, sweetness, aroma, firmness, mouth feel and general acceptability. The sensory panel consisted of 20 semi trained panelists cutting across students (aged between 20 and 30 years) of Federal University of Agriculture, Makurdi.

G. NUTRITIONAL COMPOSITION

The nutritional contents of the samples were analyzed using proximate analysis according to the methods of AOAC (1990). Nutritional composition of the samples was determined as follows:

1) Moisture Content

This is a measure of the % moisture lost due to drying at a temperature of 105 °C. Moisture was determined by Standard Official Methods of Analysis of the AOAC (1990). 5.0 g of sample was weighed in triplicate and placed in washed, dried and weighed crucible. This was placed in an oven and dried at 105 °C for three hours. The sample was allowed to cool in a desiccator and then reweighed. The percentage moisture content was calculated by computing or expressing the loss in weight on drying as a fraction of the initial weight of sample used and multiplied by 100. The percentage moisture content was calculated from the equation:

$$\% \text{ moisture} = \frac{W2 - W3}{W2 - W1} \times 100$$

W1 = Initial weight of empty crucible

W2 = Weight of crucible + sample before drying and

W3 = Final weight of crucible + sample after drying

2) Total Ash

This method is based on the vaporization of water and volatiles with burning organic substances in the presence of oxygen in the air to CO₂ at a temperature of 500 °C (dry ashing). Total ash was determined by Furnace Incineration described by AOAC (1990) The ash content was determined using the ignition method. The crucibles used were thoroughly washed and pre-heated a muffle furnace to about 500 °C. 2.0 g of the oven-dried sample used in moisture determination was weighed in triplicate and placed in the pre-heated, cooled and weighed crucible and then reweighed. The crucible was covered with its lid, the number noted and then placed in a cold muffle furnace. The temperature was allowed to rise to 500 °C and the ashing carried on for three hours at this temperature. The crucible was removed from the furnace, allowed to cool in a desiccator, and reweighed. The percentage ash content was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Ash} = \frac{\text{Weight of Ash}}{\text{Weight of original sample}} \times 100$$

3) Crude Fibre

The fibre content of the sample is a measure of the undigested particles. Crude fibre was determined using the method of (AOAC, 1990). 5g of samples were weighed into a 1dm³ conical flask. Water (100 cm³) and 20 cm³ of 20 % H₂SO₄ were added and boiled gently for 30 min. The content was filtered through whatman No.1 filter paper. The residue was scrapped back into the flask with a spatula. Water (100 cm³) and 20 cm³ of 10 % NaOH were added and allowed to boil gently for 30 min. The content was filtered and the residue was washed thoroughly with hot distilled water, and then rinsed once with 10 % HCl and twice with ethanol and finally three times with petroleum ether. It was allowed to dry and scrapped into the crucible and dried overnight at 100 °C in an air oven. It was then

removed and cooled in desiccator. The sample was weighed and ashed at 600 °C for 60 min in a muffle furnace. It was finally cooled in desiccator and weighed again. The percentage crude fiber was calculated as per the formula:

$$\% \text{ crude fiber} = \frac{\text{Weight after drying} \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample}}$$

4) Total Fat

The method makes use of polar solvents to dissolve fat where the solvent is evaporated leaving the fat content. Determination of crude fat content of the samples was done using Soxhlet type of the direct solvent extraction method. 3.0 g of the dried sample was weighed in triplicate and secured in soxhlet extraction thimble. The thimble was then put into 20 cm³ capacity soxhlet extractor. A washed, oven-dried 100 cm³ round-bottomed flask was weighed and approximately 60 cm³ of the 40-60 °C boiling range petroleum ether added to it. The flask was then mounted on the heating mantle and connected to the extractor (with condenser). The condenser and heating mantle were then activated and extraction carried on for four hours. At the end of extraction, the solvent was evaporated and the flask dried in the oven (at 60 °C). The flask was then cooled and reweighed. The percentage fat was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ fat} = \frac{\text{Weight of fat} \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample}}$$

5) Crude Protein

The crude protein content of the samples was determined using the Microkjeldahl method of AOAC (1990), which involved protein digestion and distillation. The percentage crude protein was calculated from the % Nitrogen as:

% crude protein = % N x F, where, F (conversion factor), is equivalent to 6.25.

6) Carbohydrate (Nitrogen Free Extract NFE)

The total percentage carbohydrate content was determined by the difference method as reported by Onyeike et al. (1995). This method involved adding the total values of crude protein, lipid, crude fibre, moisture and ash constituents of the sample and subtracting it from 100. The value obtained was the percentage carbohydrate constituent of the sample. Thus, % carbohydrate = 100 – (% moisture + % crude fibre + % protein + % lipid + % ash).

7) Mineral Elements Determination

Mineral elements determined are: Iron, Calcium, Magnesium, Zinc, Copper, Manganese, Lead and Cadmium.

PROCEDURE: The sample was digested using acid digestion by adding 20 ml of H₂SO₄ and 10 ml of HNO₃ (2:1). The mixture was heated on a bunsen burner until the brown fumes subsides. Addition of 10 ml of HNO₃ continued at the interval of 10 minutes and heated until the solution turned colourless. The digested samples were analyzed for the minerals using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (Sogo-Temi et al., 2014).

H. ANALYSIS OF ANTIOXIDANT ENZYMES

1) Extraction For Antioxidant Enzymes (Crude Extract)

Frozen peel tissues were ground with a mortar and pestle under liquid nitrogen. The resultant extract was homogenized in 50 mL of 100 mM, sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.8) containing 1 mM ascorbic acid and 0.5 % (w/v) polyvinylpyrrolidone, 2 mM EDTA for 5 min at 4°C. The resultant homogenate was filtered through three layers of cheese cloth and then the filtrate was centrifuged at 5000 x g for 15 min and then the supernatants were collected.

2) Measurement Of Peroxidase (POX) Activity

Total POX was measured using the method of Rao et al. (1996) with some modifications. The reaction mixture contained 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) with 2.7 mM guaiacol and 4 mM H₂O₂ and 50 µg of crude extract. Changes in absorbance at 470 nm were recorded for a period of 10 min. and activity was expressed in optical density (OD) at 470 nm.mg-1 protein.

3) Measurement Of Ascorbate Peroxidase (APX) Activity

APX activity was determined using the method described by Nakano and Asada (1981). The reaction mixture contained 90 mM potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.0), 0.1 mM EDTA, 0.65 mM ascorbate and 1 mM H₂O₂ and 50 µg of crude extract. APX activity was determined by following the H₂O₂ decomposition of ascorbate at 290nm.

4) Measurement Of Catalase (CAT) Activity

CAT activity was measured according to method described by Aebi (1983). The reaction mixture contained 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.0), 2 mM H₂O₂ and 1mM EDTA and 50 µg of crude extract. H₂O₂ oxidation was measured at 240 nm using the extinction coefficient of H₂O₂. Activity was expressed as µmol H₂O₂/min/mg protein.

I. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Results were analysed using the SPSS software version (18. SPSS) and were reported as mean ± standard deviation. Data were analysed using ANOVA followed by Duncan' s multiple range post hoc test. Significance difference was set at p ≤ 0.05.

III. RESULTS

1) Effects Of Calcium Carbide On The Ripening Time Of Bananas

The results in Table 1 shows that all the banana pulp treated with 4 g/kg calcium carbide (GRP 2) ripened within 3 days (72 hours) while the bananas treated with 8 g/kg calcium carbide (GRP 3) had a ripening time of 2 days (48 hours), and GRP 4 bananas (naturally ripened bananas) had the longest ripening time of 7 days (168 hours).

Table 1: The effect of calcium carbide on the ripening time of bananas

Samples	CaC ₂ (g/kg)	Ripening Time (days)	Shelf Life (days)
GRP 2	4	3	9
GRP 3	8	2	6
GRP 4	0	7	15

GRP 2 – Ripened bananas with 4g of CaC₂, GRP 3 – Ripened bananas with 8g of CaC₂, GRP 4 – Naturally ripened bananas (PTC)

2) Effect of Calcium Carbide on Sensory Properties of Banana Samples

Table 2 shows the sensory properties of the samples of banana analyzed. There was a significant ($p \leq 0.05$) difference in the

Table 2: Sensory Properties of the Analysed Bananas

Samples	CaC ₂ (g/kg)	Appearance	Sweetness	Aroma	Firmness	Mouthfeel	Acceptability
GRP 1	0	2.22 ± 0.32 ^a	0.23 ± 0.18 ^a	0.32 ± 0.15 ^a	5.50 ± 0.22 ^c	0.23 ± 0.14 ^a	2.23 ± 0.25 ^a
GRP 2	4 g	5.42 ± 0.55 ^b	2.89 ± 0.11 ^b	3.25 ± 0.13 ^b	3.98 ± 0.23 ^a	2.98 ± 0.99 ^b	3.33 ± 0.46 ^b
GRP 3	8 g	5.43 ± 0.33 ^b	4.33 ± 0.89 ^c	4.12 ± 0.21 ^c	5.12 ± 0.23 ^c	4.12 ± 0.30 ^d	4.43 ± 0.34 ^c
GRP 4	0	5.40 ± 0.23 ^b	2.89 ± 0.67 ^b	3.21 ± 0.45 ^b	4.43 ± 0.22 ^b	3.22 ± 0.24 ^c	3.23 ± 0.56 ^b

GRP 1 – Unripe bananas (NGC) GRP 2 – Ripened bananas with 4g of CaC₂ GRP 3 – Ripened bananas with 8g of CaC₂ GRP 4 – Naturally ripened bananas (PTC)

3) Effects Of Calcium Carbide On Nutrient Quality Of Banana Samples

Table 3 shows the nutritional analysis (proximate) of the samples analyzed. Group 1 and 2 are significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) different from group 3 and 4 in moisture content. Group 4 had the highest moisture content at 77.78 ± 0.80 while group 2 had the least moisture content at 69.40 ± 1.54 . Fat content ranged between 0.65 ± 0.01 and 0.81 ± 0.06 . Fat content decreased in ripened banana from 0.81 ± 0.06 (GRP 4) to 0.65 ± 0.01 in unripened banana (GRP 1) which is the lowest. The fibre content for GRP 1 was the highest at 3.03 ± 0.06 with GRP 2 having the least at 1.83 ± 0.04 . Ash content ranged between 1.59 ± 0.09 and 2.78 ± 0.13 with GRP 1 having the significant ($p \leq 0.05$) highest ash content when compared with the rest of the groups. The carbohydrate content of the bananas ranged between 15.23 ± 0.92 and 24.39 ± 3.04 , with GRP 2 having the highest content.

appearance of sample NGC (GRP 1) which was fully green compared to the other groups. GRP 3 had the best appearance at 5.43 ± 0.33 and also the highest acceptability at 4.43 ± 0.34 . The sweetness of the samples ranged between 0.23 ± 0.18 in GRP 1 and 4.33 ± 0.89 in GRP 3. The aroma was lowest in unripe banana (GRP 1) at 0.32 ± 0.15 while GRP 3 had the highest aroma at 4.12 ± 0.21 . The firmness was observed to be highest in the unripe banana (GRP 1) at 5.50 ± 0.22 which is statistically ($p \leq 0.05$) different from all other groups: (GRP 2, 3 and 4) which had 3.98 ± 0.23 , 5.12 ± 0.23 and 4.43 ± 0.22 respectively. The mouth feel and acceptability were significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) higher in GRP 3 than the rest of the groups while the unripe banana (GRP 1) had the least.

Table 3: Nutrient quality of banana samples

	MOISTURE %	FAT %	ASH %	FIBRE %	PROTEIN %	CHO %
GRP 1	69.40 ± 1.54 ^a	0.65 ± 0.01 ^a	2.78 ± 0.13 ^c	3.03 ± 0.06 ^d	2.22 ± 0.05 ^c	21.89 ± 1.51 ^{bc}
GRP 2	69.79 ± 3.11 ^a	0.68 ± 0.01 ^b	2.03 ± 0.06 ^b	1.83 ± 0.04 ^a	1.27 ± 0.01 ^a	24.39 ± 3.04 ^c
GRP 3	76.50 ± 0.70 ^b	0.72 ± 0.04 ^c	1.78 ± 0.03 ^a	2.06 ± 0.03 ^b	1.66 ± 0.09 ^b	16.88 ± 0.71 ^{ab}
GRP 4	77.78 ± 0.80 ^b	0.81 ± 0.06 ^d	1.59 ± 0.09 ^a	2.32 ± 0.08 ^c	2.25 ± 0.13 ^c	15.23 ± 0.92 ^a

GRP 1 – Unripe bananas (NGC) GRP 2 – Ripened bananas with 4g of CaC₂ GRP 3 – Ripened bananas with 8g of CaC₂ GRP 4 – Naturally ripened bananas (PTC)

4) *Effect Of Calcium Carbide On Mineral Composition Of Banana Samples*

The result for the effect of CaC₂ on the mineral composition of the banana samples analysed is presented in table 4. There was a decrease in Pb content during ripening. The naturally ripened bananas with no ripening agent (GRP 4) and GRP 2 had the lowest Pb value at 0.02 ± 0.01, while GRP 1 (unripe banana) had significant (p ≤ 0.05) highest value of 0.07 ± 0.01. The

highest contents of Zn and Mg at 6.08 ± 0.08 and 9.12 ± 0.37 respectively, were recorded in GRP 4 (naturally ripened banana). There were significant (p ≤ 0.05) difference in the Mn, Ca and Cd contents (2.42 ± 0.12, 2.24 ± 0.20 and 1.46 ± 0.05 respectively) in the banana treated with 8 g/kg CaC₂ (GRP 3) when compared with the rest of the groups. Cu content ranged from 0.38 ± 0.01 in GRP 4 to 1.64 ± 0.09 in GRP 1.

Table 4: The effect of calcium carbide on the mineral composition of banana samples

Samples	Lead (ppm)	Copper (ppm)	Zinc (ppm)	Manganese (ppm)	Magnesium (ppm)	Calcium (ppm)	Iron (ppm)
GRP 1	0.07 ± 0.01 ^b	1.64 ± 0.09 ^c	5.29±0.85 ^b	0.20 ± 0.05 ^a	8.92 ± 0.52 ^b	0.00 ± 0.00 ^a	ND
GRP 2	0.02 ± 0.01 ^a	0.89 ± 0.22 ^b	2.19±0.18 ^a	0.39 ± 0.12 ^a	8.06 ± 1.03 ^b	1.42 ± 0.48 ^b	ND
GRP 3	0.03 ± 0.01 ^a	0.50 ± 0.03 ^a	1.99±0.48 ^a	2.42 ± 0.12 ^b	4.49 ± 0.21 ^a	2.24 ± 0.20 ^c	ND
GRP 4	0.02 ± 0.01 ^a	0.38 ± 0.01 ^a	6.08±0.08 ^b	0.14 ± 0.03 ^a	9.12 ± 0.37 ^b	0.00 ± 0.00 ^a	ND

GRP 1 – Unripe bananas (NGC) GRP 2 – Ripened bananas with 4g of CaC₂ GRP 3 – Ripened bananas with 8g of CaC₂ GRP 4 – Naturally ripened bananas (PTC)

5) *Effect Of Calcium Carbide On Antioxidant Enzyme Activity Of Banana Samples*

Table 5 shows the effect of calcium carbide on some antioxidant enzymes (catalase, peroxidase and ascorbate peroxidase). The peroxidase activity was significantly (p ≤ 0.05) higher in GRP 4 at 3.42 ± 0.05 U/mL than the rest of the groups. There was no statistical (p ≤ 0.05) difference in the ascorbate peroxidase and catalase activities of the banana samples groupings.

Table 5: Antioxidant Enzyme Activity of the Analyzed Bananas

Sample	POX (U/mL)	APX (U/mL)	CAT U/mL)
GRP 1	1.59 ± 0.06 ^a	28.15 ± 9.61 ^a	0.39 ± 0.25 ^a
GRP 2	1.65 ± 0.05 ^a	29.67 ± 10.45 ^a	0.53 ± 0.28 ^a
GRP 3	1.99 ± 0.19 ^b	31.73 ± 2.40 ^a	0.38 ± 0.24 ^a
GRP 4	3.42 ± 0.05 ^c	33.79 ± 2.15 ^a	0.68 ± 0.15 ^a

GRP 1 – Unripe bananas (NGC) GRP 2 – Ripened bananas with 4g of CaC2 GRP 3 – Ripened bananas with 8g of CaC2 GRP 4 – Naturally ripened bananas (PTC)

IV. DISCUSSION

The findings of this research on the effects of calcium carbide on ripening time concurs with the results presented by Adeyemi et al., (2018) when examining the effects of biological and chemical ripening agents on the nutritional and metal composition of some fruits. Similarly, Sogo-Temi et al. (2014) demonstrated that calcium carbide ripens banana fruits quicker than when done naturally. These findings show that calcium carbide is a very good ripening agent especially at higher concentration. However, from the observation of the shelf-life period for the naturally and artificially ripened fruit, it was observed that the naturally ripen fruits have a longer shelf-life than the artificially ripened fruit.

In the result for sensory analysis presented in Table 5, highest sensory score was recorded in GRP 3 (8 g CaC2/kg banana) and least sensory score was recorded in the negative control sample (NGC). Acceptability was found to increase with increase in CaC2 concentration. The results for sensory analysis agreed with the finding of Nura et al. (2018) who reported that use of air tight chambers during calcium carbide ripening provide better sensory properties. Amarakoon et al. (1999) also recommended the use of 1g CaC2 per kilogram fruit. The result contradicts the findings reported by some researchers. Gunasekara et al. (2015) recorded low sensory scores and low level nutritional qualities in banana treated with calcium carbide and ethephon. Mahmood et al. (2013) also reported low sensory qualities in peach fruit ripened with CaC2, he also concluded that application of CaC2 as artificial ripening agent not only harms business based qualities of fruits but also greatly affects the physiochemical, nutritional and antioxidant properties of fruits. Hence the findings of this research showed that calcium carbide at the quantity used does not affect the sensory properties of the banana.

The results gotten in the nutritional analysis is in agreement with Sogo-Temi et al. (2014) and Adewole and Duruji (2010) who observed a reduction in the protein content during ripening which may be due to reduction of nitrogen during ripening. However it does not agree with Sen et al. (2012) who stated that proteins increases during ripening. The difference in the protein values during ripening of bananas may be due to varietal differences (Mohapatra et al., 2010). Banana fruit is eaten raw as it contains a good amount of nutrients. As a fruit banana is

eaten raw and used for various formulas, it is mandatory to check all the nutritional values due to harmful practices of artificial ripening. However the protein values were still within those reported in Nigeria 1.88-6.8% (Ayo-Omogie et al., 2010).

Moisture content values of 69%, 76% and 68-63% in ripe bananas reported by Abdullahi et al. (2018) is in agreement with the values (69%-77%) recorded in this findings. According to (Sen et al., 2012; Ayo-Omogie, 2010; Hakim et al., 2012), moisture content in banana pulp is observed to increase because of respiratory breakdown of starch to sugar, migration of water from peel to pulp and excess moisture formation. The high moisture content of banana contributes to its short storage life and high post-harvest loss. The carbohydrate reduction from 21.89 % to 15.23 % was in contrast with the findings of Abdullahi et al. (2018) who found an increase in carbohydrate content of the bananas during ripening; an increase was observed from 14.89% to 23.7%. This contrast may be as a result of the concentration of calcium carbide used where 4g/kg and 8g/kg were used for this experiment. According to Sen et al. (2012), one of the biochemical changes occurring during ripening is a decrease in carbohydrate content. The starch is degraded by starch degrading enzymes α and β amylases which convert starch to simple sugars (Ayo-Omogie et al., 2010).

Minerals whether macro or micro-minerals are required in the body for the maintenance of physiochemical processes essential to life. While minerals like K, Mg, Ca, Zn, Fe and Cu are considered essential, heavy metals like Pb, Cd and Sn are considered as a toxic contaminant and evidence of their requirements and essentialness for the body is weak (Soetan et al., 2010; Sobukola et al., 2010). The naturally ripened bananas with no ripening agent had the lowest Pb value- 0.02ppm, while the unripe (GRP 1) had the highest values of 0.07ppm. Presence of Pb in fruit may be from the soil as high level of Pb was reported in different farmlands in Eastern Nigeria (Adeyemi et al., 2018) and in fruits like banana, apple and pineapple in Lagos, Nigeria (Saranada, 2010). The presence of Pb detected in the ripened bananas could also be due to the type of storage/packaging material used during ripening. The degree of toxicity of heavy metals to the body depends on the daily intake and since these metals are non-biodegradable, there is concern if it continues to be taken by the body over time. Micro-mineral deficiency is of great concern in developing countries especially among little children (Adeyemi et al., 2018). Minerals are involved in the metabolic activities during ripening in the form of micro and macro mineral (Soetan et al., 2010).

Catalase and peroxidase are one of the most important antioxidant enzymes involved in scavenging active oxygen species in plants (Huang et al., 2007). Catalase may be the major antioxidant enzyme involved in plant defense mechanism because it is induced during heating and persists during cold storage (Sala and Lafuente, 2000). Peroxidase participates in a great number of physiological processes such as the biosynthesis of lignin, it is also regarded as one of the most heat stable enzymes in plants and its resistance to heat was reported by (Satya, 2014). According to enzyme activity results, calcium carbide reduced the activity of the antioxidant enzymes tested at 4g and 8g concentration. The research agrees with the findings that showed that banana pulp is rich in antioxidant

enzymes (Satya, 2014), and which suggested the pharmacological preparation of antioxidants.

V. CONCLUSION

This study has determined the effect of artificial ripening agents on properties of banana. It has confirmed other research work that artificial ripening accelerates ripening, but affects the nutritional quality of the fruits. It was observed that the naturally ripened fruits have a longer shelf-life than the calcium carbide artificially ripened fruits.

All the sensory properties studied were found to increase with increase in CaC₂ concentration with highest sensory scores recorded in sample treated with 8g CaC₂ per kg banana. Based on the results, it can be that said calcium carbide lowered the activity of the antioxidant enzymes tested.

The use of CaC₂ in artificial ripening of banana and other fruits should be regulated by authorities in Nigeria. Natural ripening agents should be used in ripening of banana and other fruits to shun the potential health risk associated with consumption of fruits artificially ripen with CaC₂.

VI. REFERENCES

- A.O.A.C. (1990). Official Methods of Analysis of the Association of Official Analytical Chemists, 15th edition. Arlington VA: Association of Official Analytical Chemists. pp. 1058-1059.
- Abdullahi, N., Munir, A. D. and Naja'atu, R. W. (2018). Effects of artificial ripening of banana (*Musa spp*) using calcium carbide on acceptability and nutritional quality. *Journal of Postharvest Technology*, 06(2): 14-20.
- Adeniji, T. A., Sanni, L. O., Barimala, I. S. and Hart, A.D. (2007). Nutritional and Anti-Nutritional Composition of Flour Made from Plantain and Banana Hybrid Pulp and Peel Mixture. *Nigerian Food Journal*, 25(2): 68-72.
- Adewole, M. B. and Duruji, R. W. (2010). Quality assessment of plantain (*Musa paradisiacal L.*) as affected by different ripening methods. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 9(38): 6290-6293.
- Adeyemi, M. M., Bawa, M. M. and Muktar, M. (2018). Evaluation of the Effect of Calcium Carbide on Induce Ripening of Banana, Pawpaw and Mango cultivated within Kaduna Metropolis, *Nigerian Journal of Chemistry Society, Nigeria*, 43(2): 108 - 118.
- Aebi, H. E. (1983). Catalase in Vitro. *Methods in Enzymology*, 105: 121-126.
- Ahenkora, K.M., Key, A., Marfo, K. and Banful, B. (1997). Nutritional composition of false horn Apantu pa plantain during ripening and processing. *African Crop Science Journal*, 5(2). pp. 243-248.
- Ajayi, A. R and Mbah, G. O. (2007). Identification of Indigenous Ripening Technologies of Banana and Plantain Fruits Among Women-Marketers in Southeastern Nigeria. *Journal of Agriculture, Food, Environment and Extension*, 6(2): 60-66.
- Ajayi, A. R and Mbah, G. O. (2007). Identification of Indigenous Ripening Technologies of Banana and Plantain Fruits Among Women-Marketers in South Eastern Nigeria. *Journal of Agriculture, Food, Environment and Extension*, 6(2): 60-66.
- Amarakoon, R., Illeperuma, D. C. K. and Sarananda, K. H. (1999). Effect of Calcium Carbide Treatment on Ripening and Quality of Velleicolomban and Willard Mangoes. *Tropical Agricultural Research*, 11: 54-60.
- Ayo-omogie, H. N., Adeyemi, I. A. and Otunola, E. T. (2010). Effect of ripening on some physiochemical properties of cooking banana (*Musa ABB Cardaba*) pulp and flour. *International journal of food science and technology* 45:2605-2611.
- Gunasekara, S. R. W., Hemamali, K. K. G. U., Dayananada, T. G. and Jayamanne, V. S. (2015). Post Harvest Quality Analysis of 'embul' Banana following Artificial Ripening Techniques. *International Journal of Science, Environment and Technology*, 4(6): 1625-1632.
- Hakim, M. A., Obidul-Huq, A. K., Alam, M. A., Khatib, A., Saha, B. K., Haque, K. M. F. and Zaidul, I. S. M. (2012). Role of Health Hazardous Ethephon in Nutritive Values of Selected Pineapple, Banana and Tomato. *Journal Food Agriculture and Environment*, 10(2): 247-251.
- Huang, R., Xia, L., Lu, Y. and Wang, M. (2007). Antioxidant Activity and Oxygen Scavenging System in Orange Pulp during Fruit Ripening and Maturation. *Science of Horticulture*, 113: 166-172
- Kulkarni, S. G., Kudachikar, V. B. and Prakash, M. N. (2010). Studies on physico-chemical changes during artificial ripening of banana (*Musa sp*) variety 'Robusta'. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 48(6). pp. 730-734.
- Kulkarni, S. G., Kudachikar, V. B. and Prakash, M. N. (2010). Studies on Physico-Chemical Changes during Artificial Ripening of Banana (*Musa sp*) Variety 'Robusta'. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 48(6): 730-734.
- Linda, M. P., Deborah, A. M. and Gail-Band, E. L. (1991). *Laboratory Methods for Sensory Analysis of food*. Canada: Research Branch Agriculture Canada publication. Pp. 64-66
- Mahmood, T., Saeed, I., Anwer, H., Mahmood, I. and Zubair, A. (2013). Comparative Study to Evaluate the Effect of Calcium Carbide (CaC₂) as an Artificial Ripening Agent on Shelf Life, Physio-chemical Properties, Iron Containment and Quality of prunus persica l Batsch. *European Academic Research*, 1: 2286-4822
- Margard, L. U. and Briav, M. A. (1979). *Plant products of Tropical Africa*. The macmillan press limited. Chapter 6. pp. 35-36.
- Mohapatra, D., Mishra, S. and Sutar, N. (2010). Banana and its by-product utilization: an overview. *Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research*, 69: 323-329.

- Molina, A .B. and Valmayor, R. V. (1999). Banana production system in South East Asia. *INIBAP*, 10: 423-436.
- Nakano, Y. and Asaba, K. (1981). Hydrogen Peroxidase is Scavenged by Ascorbate-Specific Peroxidase in Spinach Chloroplasts. *Plant Cell Physiology*, 22: 867-880.
- Nura, N., Munir, A. D. and Naja'atu, R. W. (2018) Effects of Artificial Ripening of Banana (*Musa spp*) Using Calcium Carbide on Acceptability and Nutritional Quality. *Journal of Postharvest Technology*, 06(2): 14-20. Retrieved from: <http://www.jpht.info>
- Onyeike, E. N., Olungwe, T. and Uwakwe, A. A. (1995). Effect of Heat Treatment and Defatting on the Proximate Composition of Some Nigerian Local Soup Thickeners. *Food Chemistry* 53(2): 173-175.
- Rao, M. V., Paliyath, G. and Ormond, D. P. (1996). UV-B and Ozone Induced Biochemical Changes in Antioxidant Enzymes of *Arabidopsis Thaliana*. *Plant Physiology*, 110: 125-136.
- Sala, J. M. and Lafuente, M. T. (2000). Catalase Activity is related to Tolerance of Mandarin Fruits to Chilling. *Postharvest Biology and Technology*, 20: 81-89.
- Sanjeev, K. K. and Eswaran, A. (2008). Efficacy of Micro Nutrients on Banana Fusarium wilt (*Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. cubense*) and Its Synergistic Action with *Trichoderma Viride*. *Notulae Botanicae Horti Agrobotanici Cluj-Napoca*, 36 (1): 52-54.
- Sarananda, K. H. (2010). Effect of Calcium Carbide on Ripening of “embul” Banana (*Musa spp*). *Tropical Agriculturalist*, 146:1-7
- Satya, M. (2014). Assaying the Antioxidant Activity of Banana Peel. *American Journal of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology*, 3: 122-129
- Sen, C., Mishra, H. N. and Srivastav, P. P. (2012). Modified atmosphere packaging and active packaging of banana (*Musa spp*): A review of control of ripening and extension of shelf life. *Journal of Stored Products and Post-harvest Research*, 3(9): 122-132.
- Sngal, S., Kumud, M. and Thakral, S. (2012). Application of Apple as Ripening Agent for Banana. *Indian Journal of Natural Products and Resources*, 3(1): 61-64.
- Sobukola, O. P., Adeniran, O. M., Odedairo, A. A. and Kajihaua, O. E. (2010). Heavy Metals Levels of some Fruits and Leafy Vegetables from selected Markets in Lagos, Nigeria. *African Journal of Science*, 4(2):389-393.
- Soetan, K. O., Olaiya, C. O. and Oyewole, O. E. (2010). The Importance of Mineral Elements for Humans, Domestic Animals and Plants: A Review. *African Journal of food Science*, 4(5): 200-222.
- Sogo-Temi, C. M., Idowu, O. A. and Idowu, E. (2014). Effect of biological and chemical ripening agents on the nutritional and metal composition of Banana (*Musa spp*). *Journal of Applied Science and Environment Management*, 18(2): 243-246.
- Zewter, A., Woldetsadik, K. and Workneh, T. S. (2012). Effect of 1-methylcyclopropene, potassium permanganate and packing on quality of banana. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 7(16): 2425-2437.